

NEANIAS
**Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere,
Underwater and Space Challenges**

Deliverable Report

**Deliverable: D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements
and Specifications**

30/11/2021

NEANIAS is funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme via grant agreement No. 863448

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Document Info

Project Information			
Acronym	NEANIAS		
Name	Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges		
Start Date	1 Nov 2019	End Date	31 Oct 2022
Program	H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures		
Call ID	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-2020	Topic	H2020-INFRAEOSC-2019-1
Grant No	863448	Instrument	RIA
Document Information			
Deliverable No	D3.2		
Deliverable Title	Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications		
Due Date	30-Nov-2021	Delivery Date	17-Jan-2022
Lead Beneficiary	UBIWHERE (6)		
Beneficiaries (part.)	NOA (20); MEE0 (17); UNIMIB (11); ATHENA (2); NKUA (1);		
Editor(s)	Ricardo Vitorino (Ubiwhere)		
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Reviewer(s)	Gábor Vicze (INNOMINE)		
Workpackage No	WP3		
Version	V1.0	Stage	Final
Version details	Revision: 2 . Last save: 2022-01-17, 14:18 Pages: 7272, Characters: 101995		
Distribution	Public	Type	Report
Keywords	EOSC; Services; Cloud Computing; Atmospheric Research		

Change Record

Version	Date	Change Description	Editor	Change Location (page/section)
1.0	2022-01-17	Document version submitted to EC	Ricardo Vitorino (Ubiwhere)	

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NEANIAS is a Research and Innovation Action funded by European Union under Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, via grant agreement No. 863448. NEANIAS is project that comprehensively addresses the ‘Prototyping New Innovative Services’ challenge set out in the ‘Roadmap for EOSC’ foreseen actions. It drives the co-design, delivery, and integration into EOSC of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: underwater research, atmospheric research and space research. In each sector it engages a diverse set of research and business groups, practices, and technologies and will not only address its community-specific needs but will also enable the transition of the respective community to the EOSC concept and Open Science principles. NEANIAS provides its communities with plentiful resource access, collaboration instruments, and interdisciplinary research mechanisms, which will amplify and broaden each community’s research and knowledge generation activities. NEANIAS delivers a rich set of services, designed to be flexible and extensible, able to accommodate the needs of communities beyond their original definition and to adapt to neighbouring cases, fostering reproducibility and re-usability. NEANIAS identifies promising, cutting-edge business cases across several user communities and lays out several concrete exploitation opportunities.

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Table of Contents

1.	Introduction	9
1.1.	Context	9
1.2.	Contents and Rationale	9
1.3.	Changes from previous release report	10
1.4.	Structure of the document	10
2.	User Requirements for the Atmospheric Services	11
2.1.	Atmospheric End-user Communities	11
2.1.1.	Urban air quality authorities.....	12
2.1.2.	Geologists, Geohazards and civil protection stakeholders.....	13
2.1.3.	Meteorological services	14
2.1.4.	Energy and Power sector and industrial emitters	14
2.1.5.	Ecologists	14
2.1.6.	Rural/urban planners	14
2.1.7.	Insurance and health.....	15
2.2.	Relevant Atmospheric Datasets and Products.....	15
2.2.1.	Data and Products for Urban air quality authorities.....	15
2.2.2.	Data and Products for Geologists.....	21
2.2.3.	Data and Products for Meteorological services	24
2.3.	Atmospheric Sector: Current Software and Services	33
2.3.1.	[A1] – Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring service	33
2.3.2.	[A2] – Monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions service	39
2.3.3.	[A3] – Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service.....	43
2.4.	User Requirements for Atmospheric Services	47
3.	Co-design and Service Specifications	50
3.1.	Atmospheric services	50
3.1.1.	[A1] – Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring service	50
3.2.	NEANIAS Atmospheric Services Co-design Specifications Released.....	51
4.	Conclusions	56
	References	57
	Appendix I – ATMO-FLUD Specifications	59
	Appendix II	71

Tables of Figures & Tables

Document Figures

Figure 1- Monitar Air Quality Monitoring Station (left) and Weather station (right).	16
Figure 2 - Urban Platform real-time map.	17
Figure 3 - Urban Platform Air Quality analysis from an in-situ monitoring station.	18
Figure 4 - Urban Platform Weather analysis from an in-situ monitoring station.	18
Figure 5 - Urban Platform Air Quality analysis with customizable dashboard and charts.	19
Figure 6 - Smart Air Quality real-time map.	19
Figure 7- Smart Air Quality individual analysis from an in-situ monitoring station.	20
Figure 8 - Smart Air Quality asset management (stations and teams).	20
Figure 9 - Main active faults of Mt Etna and main historic seismic events.	23
Figure 10 - Simplified geological map of Mt Etna with main active faults and the sites of indoor radon measurements. The urbanized areas are shown in light gray. PFS, Pernicana fault system; RFS, Ragalna fault system; TFS, Timpe fault system; FF, Fiandaca fault; TF, Trecastagni fault; ATF, Aci Trezza fault.	23
Figure 11 - 2016-2018 Radon measurements recorded at Mt Etna in the Giarre municipality. Radon concentration are presented as daily (blue line), weekly (red), and long-term (green) averages. No data interruption occurred during the acquisition period.	24
Figure 12 - VOAGr MET Tower.	25
Figure 13 - VOAGr MET TOWER graphical form flux densities using different flux densities calculating methods.	26
Figure 14 - Copernicus online catalogue of data.	30
Figure 15 - ACTRiS Data Centre (an online portal for data).	31
Figure 16 - ACTRiS processing data through its portal.	32
Figure 17 - Comparison of the determination Sensible Heat fluxes by Eddy Covariance and Variances methods.	39
Figure 18 - Screenshot of the Atmo-Stress service, showing the possibility of selecting data fields from the columns of the input file.	40
Figure 19 - Screenshot of the Atmo-Stress service, showing the trajectories map of σ_3 in a rift zone in Northern Iceland, obtained with the Polynomial interpolation, global order, and visualized on the website. The result can also be downloaded.	41
Figure 20 - Examples of outputs of Atmo-Seism, obtained from input datasets collected on Mt. Etna in 2016; (a) Data vs temperature and pressure; (b) Filtered radon values; (c) Longitude vs depth of the earthquake hypocentre; (d) Released energy and radon emission	42
Figure 21- ATMO-4CAST structure for GRIB method (input files in orange).	44
Figure 22 - ATMO-4CAST air quality modelling system structure (input files in yellow).	47
Figure 23 - ATMO-FLUD Home page.	60
Figure 24 - ATMO-FLUD Algorithm selection page.	61

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 25 - ATMO-FLUD Input type selection page.	62
Figure 26 - ATMO-FLUD Job status and progress.	66
Figure 27- ATMO-FLUD sample output 1.	67
Figure 28 - ATMO-FLUD sample output 2.	67
Figure 29 - ATMO-FLUD sample output 3.	68
Figure 30 - ATMO-FLUD sample output 4.	68
Figure 31 - ATMO-FLUD user options after job completion.	69
Figure 32 - ATMO-FLUD past studies.	70

Document Tables

Table 1 - End-user communities for Atmospheric Services.	11
Table 2 - onitar's air quality parameters.	16
Table 3 - Monitar's weather parameters.	16
Table 4 - Dataset for Urban air quality authorities.	21
Table 5 - Dataset for Geologists.	21
Table 6 - Dataset for Meteorological Services.	24
Table 7 - OpenWeather Dataset from its service.	27
Table 8 - OpenWeather API conditions.	27
Table 9 - IPMA Dataset from its service.	27
Table 10 - IPMA API conditions.	28
Table 11 - DarkSky Dataset from its service.	28
Table 12 - DarkSky API conditions.	29
Table 13 - AQICN API conditions.	29
Table 14 - User Requirements for Atmospheric Services.	47
Table 15 - Acceptance criteria for user requirements.	48
Table 16 - Co-Design Specifications.	53

Abstract

The objective of deliverable D3.2 is to report on final updates of user requirements and specifications accomplished for the software development plan of the Atmospheric Research Services latest release. This document reports on Atmospheric end-user communities, involved datasets and products and the current status of the Atmospheric Services developed according to the requirements, specifications and development plan initially set on deliverable D3.1 and significantly updated with the validations of the services concerning the users' requirements and recommendations. Results of these validations are detailed in this report. Each service validation round allowed to understand the degree of user satisfaction and upgrade the services developed. Furthermore, the validations allowed checking the degree of compliance with the specifications designed to meet the user's requirements defined in D3.1. These results were obtained from surveys made to users (google forms format) which may be seen in deliverable D3.4 and D.6.

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

In the framework of WP3, NEANIAS will deliver cloud-based services that target specific challenges of the atmospheric thematic sector. WP3 embraces co-design under an agile methodology that spans all project activities, where service consumers and providers are engaged in a cycle of requirements, design, implementation/verification, evaluation and feedback. WP3 activities are amplified by engagement and onboarding activities, ensuring the potential of sustainability from the perspective of adoption and uptake. In particular, bringing together experts and know-how from Open Science, EOSC and Research Infrastructures, such as National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Università Degli Studi di Milano Bicocca and Athena Research Centre, just to name a few, NEANIAS seeks not only to satisfy the needs of the atmospheric sector communities, boarding the cloud era, but also to identify and elevate opportunities that exploit the plentiful resources (data, CPU, storage, services) at reach, weaving innovative value chains and innovative ways to conduct e-science.

In such a context, the first Task of WP3 *i.e.*, ‘*T3.1 atmospheric research sector user requirements, service co-design and gap analysis*’ has analysed information, data and requirements collected from the Atmospheric-related application domains and user communities to form this deliverable of WP3, the present document: ‘*D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on requirements, specifications*’. The NEANIAS Atmospheric services are:

- A1 (ATMO-FLUD) service, which delivers an operational workflow for estimating flux density and fluxes of gases, aerosol, energy from data obtained from specifically set meteorological stations, validated towards standardized, regularized processes.
- A2 services focused on monitoring atmospheric components in active tectonic and volcanic regions, which are two separated services: (i) ATMO-STRESS, that produces maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data; (ii) ATMO-SEISM, that relates the seismicity of an active tectonic region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere.
- A3 (ATMO-4CAST) service delivers a novel cloud-based solution that provides both weather and air quality estimation and forecast. This service enables a user to map atmospheric pollutants concentration at a local/urban level.

1.2. Contents and Rationale

This deliverable, D3.2, is a report containing the final end user requirements and the software specifications accomplished within the latest release of the Atmospheric Research Services.

The report describes the end-user communities approached to properly collect the user requirements initially reported in the deliverable D3.1 [1] and then it reports their updates and refinements gathered thanks to the service developed and their validation in each service release. Finally, it presents the mapping of the requirements with the technical specifications accomplished during the implementation and release of A1, A2 and A3 services.

1.3. Changes from previous release report

The initial content and main structure of this document has been given by D3.1 [1] reporting the initial user requirements, service specifications and software development plan. Section 2.3. has been updated with the current state of each service developed under Atmospheric thematic, especially regarding the inputs necessary to run each service. Therefore, the Chapter 4 of D3.1 has been removed. Also, Chapter 3 has been updated according to the maturity level reached by the atmospheric services and the results of the services assessment and validations from D3.4 [2] and D3.6 [3].

1.4. Structure of the document

The deliverable is structured in five sections (chapters), being the first one responsible for introducing the report, briefly mentioning its content and how it is structured. Chapter 2 describes the Atmospheric end-user communities (section 2.1), their datasets and products (section 2.2), the current state of the software and services employed (section 2.3) and the requirements (section 2.4). Chapter 3 presents the current status of the services after user's validation and highlight the technical software specifications to address the requirements. Finally, Chapter 4 outlines the conclusions.

2. User Requirements for the Atmospheric Services

This chapter aims at defining the user requirements of the project. To do so, first, the target communities will be identified (who they are, their needs and how NEANIAS can help them), and then current existing products and datasets will be listed and described, which will help in identifying tools and sources that can be helpful in designing, implementing and testing NEANIAS services. Finally, current software and services will be studied and detailed to understand which tools can help in the development of the project. With this, it will be possible to define the user requirements of the project.

2.1. Atmospheric End-user Communities

In this section, target end-user communities are identified, where it is described who they are, what they need (in the form of user stories) and how NEANIAS can help achieve such purpose. This is an important step in understanding what to do along the project, since the developed product must be useful and valuable to its end-users. The end-user communities for the Atmospheric Services are listed below, being analysed in more detail afterwards.

Table 1 - End-user communities for Atmospheric Services.

End-user Community	Brief Description
Urban air quality authorities	Monitor the air quality in cities or urban environments to track the performance of environmental policies and ensure the quality of life of citizens, interested in calculating the energy and anthropogenic energy fluxes as well as greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions fluxes.
Geologists	Study the solid, liquid, and gaseous matter that constitutes the Earth, interested in tracking and calculating gas fluxes from active faults, fractures and volcanic vents in relation to tectonic stresses.
Geohazards, civil protection	Focused on the protection of citizens from natural disasters, and using the principles of emergency operations (prevention, mitigation, preparation, response, or emergency evacuation and recovery), this community is interested on the assessment of dangerous areas regarding the air quality and gases emissions.
Meteorological services	Providing weather forecasts, warnings of hazardous weather, and other weather-related products to organisations and the public for the purposes of protection, safety, and general information, these are interested in calculating GHG emissions fluxes, to validate national inventories.
Energy and power sector and industrial air pollutant emitters	With the business of producing energy or resources through industry facilities, these communities need to calculate GHG emissions, specific pollutant fluxes as well as energy fluxes, to ensure compliance with regulations and benchmark their environmental and energy performance.
Ecologists	Study the interactions of organisms and their biophysical environments, by analysing their abundance, distribution and biodiversity, monitoring the ecological relationships and how they regulate the flux of energy, nutrients, and climate all the way up to the planetary scale. This community is interested in tracking and

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

	analysing the dynamic history of the planetary atmosphere's CO ₂ and O ₂ composition and how it has been affected by the biogenic flux of gases coming from respiration and photosynthesis, in relation to the ecology and evolution of plants and animals.
Rural/urban planners	Organising and monitoring socio-economic activities and initiatives to manage the spatial organisation of regions for efficient allocation of land use and improve standard of living, either in cities or rural areas. Depending on how these planning outcomes are applied, they can improve air quality in the long run, by strategic location of polluting sources and exposed population, and encouraging a structure that would minimise pollution emissions, hence the interest in tracking the GHG emissions fluxes, as well as energy fluxes.
Insurance, health	With the purpose of ensuring their customers or patients safest conditions, where the level of pollutants prescribed by regulations must not be exceeded during a given time in a defined area, these communities need to access atmospheric data about the GHG and pollutants emissions to validate incidents and cross-check with policies.

2.1.1. Urban air quality authorities

Urban air quality authorities seek to better understand human activity's effect on air quality and the environment. Since anthropogenic energy fluxes and GHG emission fluxes have a big impact on several sectors like agriculture and health, it is essential to have the proper tools for monitoring greenhouse gas flux density as well as for air quality estimation, monitoring, and forecasting. To achieve that, it is necessary to automate and validate existing software modules for these two main ambitions.

The first one, monitoring greenhouse gas flux density is achievable using data obtained from specifically set meteorological stations, integrated as a novel cutting-edge service into EOSC. For that, an orchestrator will be built to select the optimal method or combination of methods, for processing, depending on the dataset, that can be uploaded by the user.

The second one, air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting, is achieved with the implementation of an air quality modelling system that will provide the spatial distribution of pollutants concentration in urban context. Therefore, a novel urban air quality system able to provide the dispersion of pollutants with a high spatial resolution is being integrated as a novel cutting-edge service into EOSC. With the previous objectives completed, it becomes possible for urban authorities not only to improve their analysis on the existing datasets and to achieve better results, but also to build and improve forecast and monitoring services. Usually, the studies that enable to understand urban air quality are developed and provided by universities and air quality research centres, which then report the outcomes for urban authorities. There are several research centres and universities that have dedicated groups in air quality fields worldwide (in Greece, Italy, Slovenia, Portugal, Brazil, Spain, United Kingdom, France and others). Therefore, we believe that at least an amount of 200 users might approach the developed services. Some examples of these research centres are GEMAC from University of Aveiro (around 22 members) and CITTA from University of Coimbra and Porto (around 10 potential users).

2.1.2. Geologists, Geohazards and civil protection stakeholders

The geologists' community working on geohazards needs to better understand the relationships between different phenomena that can affect civil society. A great concern is represented by gases released in volcanic areas (including radon, SO₂, CO₂) that have serious health negative effects, as well as by ashes produced by volcanic eruptions. The latter also has an impact on health, along with important problems to air traffic and other infrastructures.

Particularly, Radon emission depends on a series of other phenomena such as atmospheric pressure, temperature variation, and changes of stresses acting on the fractures from which gas is outpoured. The geological community has asked NEANIAS to release services capable of cross-correlating the time series of data regarding gas emission, atmospheric conditions and earthquake occurrence, possibly to be also applied to CO₂ and SO₂ series from multiscale database (e.g. spanning from satellite data to field-collected ones). The latter process is composed of several variables that comprehend the surface distance between the gas emission point and the earthquake epicentre location, the distance between the gas emission point and the depth of the earthquake hypocentre, the tectonic stress characteristics (fault kinematics trajectories of the principal stresses obtainable from the earthquake focal mechanism solution), and the Magnitude of the seismic event, and the spatial resolution of data. It is thus necessary to develop a service capable of cross-correlating all these parameters in order to distinguish which is the dominant process in dictating the variations of gas radon emission, and possibly also to CO₂ and SO₂.

The emission of gases and ashes from the summit crater of an active volcano such as Etna or Stromboli, are dependent upon the endogenous dynamic of the magma into the volcanic conduit, thus mainly related to the pressure dependent on the three-phases fluid system, and upon the stress state of the host rock surrounding the conduit, which is to say the volcanic edifice. Earthquake occurrence can change the local stress state favouring gas flux by stress unclamping. The geological community is asking to NEANIAS to release services capable of cross-correlating the time series of data regarding gas emission, earthquake occurrence, and stress changes. Again, earthquake occurrence means that the service must be capable of correlating the distance of the earthquake epicentre and hypocentre location from the crater, the tectonic stress characteristics (fault kinematics trajectories of the principal stresses obtainable from the earthquake focal mechanism solution), and the Magnitude of the seismic event.

The software can be released in three phases addressing incrementally more complex datasets and scenarios towards analysing efficiently the variation in gas concentrations before during and after a seismic event. The software will be tested against the detection of changes in ash and gas concentration at regions with active volcanoes (e.g. Etna and Stromboli in Italy, Santorini in Greece), which constitutes a targeted application of significant importance for assessing geohazards and risks.

The geological community also needs the implementation of a service capable of calculating and visualize the stress trajectories in plan and 3D view. A basic C implemented software called "Lissage" program from Lee and Angelier (1994) [4] can calculate stress trajectory in 2D (maps) but has several limitations, it is not user-friendly, does not consider different data sources (e.g. field data, focal mechanisms, earthquakes)

and, finally, it does not provide a 3D or an automatic 2D-layered output compatible with common GIS workspace (e.g. ArcMap, QGIS, Google Earth) and Matlab/Excel.

The existing software comes from: Lee, J. C., Angelier, J., 1994. Paleostress trajectory maps based on the results of local determinations: the “Lissage” program. *Computers & Geosciences*, 20(2), 161-191.

To validate the services and collect feedback about them from the geological community, 2 authorities from Italy and Iceland (Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Italy, and University of Iceland) have been approached, for a total of about 30 users. More authorities can be approached in the next months for further validation, both in the academic sector and in Civil Protection Agencies, in order to increase the number of users.

2.1.3. Meteorological services

Air quality forecast and estimations are highly dependent on weather parameters, which may be estimated by meteorological services. The weather forecast usually requires supercomputers working in parallel. With the new generation of developed services in the cloud, the amount of the computational demand required by this type of models is feasible, avoiding the cost of instantiating such model. Therefore, we estimate that same research centres presented in 2.1.1 might also be interested in the weather forecast service (A3) developed in the NEANIAS project.

2.1.4. Energy and Power sector and industrial emitters

Once the requirement to obtain GHGs fluxes from the sectors Energy, Power and other Industrial emitters has been legislated, their requirements to submit GHGs emissions will emerge. This requirement will not be based on inventories of material used and accompanying algorithms but on “point” and “area” source measurements. Therefore, the atmospheric services shall be able to query location parameters (e.g., a tuple of coordinates, a street name, a polygon or area or other geography type of data), besides the time intervals, so industry operators become able to benchmark their services, perform audits and confirm they comply with the regulation and policies.

2.1.5. Ecologists

Our services described from 2.1.1 to 2.1.4 will help them to establish the validity of the above sector’s presentation of results, i.e. leveraging gases fluxes monitoring to evaluate the atmosphere composition and compare with the ecosystem’s evolution.

2.1.6. Rural/urban planners

Planners of urban or rural areas need a reliable service that provides them with sustainable indicators of the environment such as Fine particulate (PM_{2.5}) and particulate (PM₁₀) concentration, as well as greenhouse gas emissions measured in tonnes per capita, so as to correlate with the demographic information available. Moreover, and especially considering the pandemic faced from late 2019 to 2020, due to COVID-19, it is important to monitor the impact of these particulates and spread of respiratory pandemics, as some studies alert to. Therefore, the Atmospheric services must be able to provide standard Key Performance Indicators about these conditions for

a certain area and period of time. In order to understand and enable rural/urban planners to make decisions towards sustainable policies, usually is necessary to make long-term analysis and scenarios analysis, in a way of choosing the best approach. Some examples are Transport entities, which are one of the main contributors to urban atmospheric pollution, therefore usually they need the information of the environmental impact of their transports for regulatory purposes.

2.1.7. Insurance and health

Similar to 2.1.6, the services will allow insurance or health communities to validate incidents and cross-check with policies, therefore, the services shall support thresholds as query parameters to request all data of a certain area that was under or above a given threshold. Moreover, the spatial distribution of air pollutants at a urban/local level will facilitate to understand air quality hotspots and understand the exposure of some communities to certain harmful pollutants. These outcomes are quite important to research centres/ universities and indoor and outdoor air quality monitoring companies. An amount of 19 authorities (around at least 57 potential users) in these domains were approached covering 8 European Countries (Italy, Portugal Spain, Greece, Germany, Belgium and Malta).

2.2. Relevant Atmospheric Datasets and Products

In this section, various atmospheric datasets and products are identified, which will be helpful to understand what is available that can be useful within the project, be it data that can be used to test the project or products that can be either used to provide some sort of service to the project, or serve as a guideline to define some feature.

2.2.1. Data and Products for Urban air quality authorities

The city of Porto makes air quality data openly available through their urban data platform's portal¹, where the data is free and open, following FIWARE data models and open standards. It uses Monitar's Air Quality and Weather stations², which follow the directive 2008/50/EC. The air quality stations monitor air quality gaseous parameters with constant flow sampling and particulate filtration and can also integrate other air quality sensors. The communication is done using the 3G/4G network or Wi-Fi networks, when available.

¹ <http://history-data.urbanplatform.portodigital.pt/v2/ui/#/queries>

² <https://www.monitar.pt/>

Figure 1- Monitar Air Quality Monitoring Station (left) and Weather station (right).

The following tables represent some of the solution’s main characteristics regarding the parameters that the air quality stations and the weather stations can measure.

Table 2 - onitar’s air quality parameters.

Parameter	Range
O3	10 – 1000 ppb
NO2	0.05 - 0.5 ppm
CO	0 – 1000 ppm
CO2	0 – 5000 ppm
PM1	0 –100 µg/m ³
PM2.5	0 – 100 µg/m ³
Volatile organic compounds (VOCs)	1 – 1000 ppm

Table 3 - Monitar’s weather parameters.

Parameter	Range	Accuracy
Temperature	-40 – 125 °C	±0.3 °C
Relative humidity	0 – 100 %	±2 %
Wind direction	0 – 360 °	± 3°±5%
Wind speed	0 – 89 m/s	0.5 m/s or ±5%
Rain fall	0 – 999.8 mm	± 0.2 mm or ±4 %
Solar radiation	0 – 1800 W/m ²	± 5%
UV radiation	0 – 16 index	± 5 %

Regarding the products for Urban air quality authorities, the following software solutions are available:

2.2.1.1. Urban Platform

The Urban Platform³ consists of a multitenant software platform capable of collecting, storing, analysing and publishing (as open data, when needed) multi-domain

³ Urban Platform - <https://urbanplatform.city>

information, provisioned by different sources such as sensor networks, Open Data catalogues as well as information systems and mobile applications.

Figure 2 - Urban Platform real-time map.

The Urban Platform is a solution that provides in real-time a holistic view of a city or region, with an interactive map displaying georeferenced information about the different verticals/use cases (traffic, parking, public transports, air quality, energy, street lighting, waste management, water leakage, and flow level, electric charging, energy, street lighting, waste management, water leakage and flow level, electric charging, and noise level), plus the capability of focusing on or zooming in specific pins and filtering the data per vertical solution or region in an always-visible element, offering an easy way for users to search for the relevant information. All information is represented in a rich way with multiple criteria such as colour, dimension and icon types, providing an easy way to understand the overall status of the city at any given moment.

Figure 3 - Urban Platform Air Quality analysis from an in-situ monitoring station.

Despite all the domains that the Urban Platform can accommodate, the most relevant for this case is the Weather and Air Quality. The two images (the one above and the other below) show two scenarios for different locations where it is possible to see a detailed view of the air quality measured by a station and the weather parameters measured.

Figure 4 - Urban Platform Weather analysis from an in-situ monitoring station.

Besides the visualisation of real-time and historical information, the Urban Platform also calculates some insights, as it is possible to see in the following image, by correlating information such as traffic congestion with air quality index for a specific area or region, but also to have some insights based on historical data, for example, the noise level observations per hour and per weekday.

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 5 - Urban Platform Air Quality analysis with customizable dashboard and charts.

2.2.1.2. Smart Air Quality

Smart Air Quality is a cloud solution for smart cities that focuses on air quality monitoring, which allows public authorities to have a detailed view of all the city air quality stations and allows to take some insights into the overall air quality. It collects and stores the data provided by air quality stations (IoT devices) that communicate in real-time through wireless networks. The solution then makes the data available through open and interoperable REST APIs (so they can be shared with the community) and responsive user interfaces that adapt to the device's screen dimensions, to be used by expert staff from the smart city.

Figure 6 - Smart Air Quality real-time map.

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Besides allowing the end-users to identify and access air quality measurements from individual stations, it provides a system for asset and event management, to control and manage each station individually and the data collected by it.

Figure 7- Smart Air Quality individual analysis from an in-situ monitoring station.

Besides this, it provides operational features where administrators can see the operational status of devices and dispatch teams to fix the ones not working properly or technicians to integrate new ones.

Figure 8 - Smart Air Quality asset management (stations and teams).

2.2.1.3. Dataset for Urban air quality authorities

The following table describes the datasets that urban air quality authorities shall get access to with the thematic service A3:

Table 4 - Dataset for Urban air quality authorities.

DATASETS – A3			
id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source
1	Porto Air Quality	REST API for real-time and historical data on air quality monitored from 5 stations (O3, NO2, CO, CO2, PM10, PM2.5, Volatile organic compounds)	Porto Urban Data Platform (Monitar)
2	Porto Weather	REST API for real-time and historical data on weather monitored from 7 stations (Temperature, Relative humidity, Wind direction, Wind speed, Rain fall, Solar radiation, UV radiation)	Porto Urban Data Platform (Monitar)
3	Porto Weather forecast	REST API for weather forecast for a given day	IPMA & OpenWeather
4	Porto Air Quality Index	REST API for air quality index calculation	AQICN
5	Satellite Air Quality	REST API providing: Ozone (O3), Nitrogen Dioxide (NO2), Sulphur Dioxide (SO2, Carbon Monoxide (CO), Methane (CH4), Formaldehyde (HCHO), UV Aerosol Index	MEE0 – Sentinel-5P Data

While Porto’s Air Quality and Weather data has already been described before, the two other datasets are described in a later section. The dataset from MEE0 was defined in a joint effort with WP4 and WP6.

2.2.2. Data and Products for Geologists

The following table describes the dataset required for geologists for thematic service A2:

Table 5 - Dataset for Geologists.

DATASETS – A2			
id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source
1	Gas radon from Mt Etna faults	Excel table of values of gas radon emitted from the faults of Etna volcano	National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, Italy

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

2	Gas and ash plumes from Etna crater	Excel table of values of various gases and ashes emitted from the summit vents of Etna	National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, Italy
3	Gas from Nea Kameni volcano, Greece	Excel table of values of various gases emitted from the fractures on Nea Kameni volcano, Santorini	Surveys by researchers of various universities
4	Map of all Etna faults	Database containing the georeferenced data of all faults on Mt Etna	National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, Italy
5	Seismicity of Mt Etna	Database containing all foci and M of earthquakes that occurred at Etna in the last tens of years	National Institute of Geophysics and Volcanology, Italy
6	Meteorological data of each site	Excel tables of meteorological data	
7	Thermal anomalies at selected volcanoes	CSV table	MODIS/MODVOLC
8	SO ₂ columns from satellites at various volcanoes	CSV table	Global Volcanism Program

The above listed datasets represent information about the two main components of processes that are related to the geological needs represented in the NEANIAS project: the atmospheric component and the solid Earth component. Regarding the atmospheric component, the team has already collected relevant data series on the gas emission from various volcanoes, namely Mt Etna in Italy and Nea Kameni in Santorini, Greece. The data series are more complete for Mt Etna having been collected in the last years each 20 minutes by installed instruments that were continuously monitoring the gas radon flux. On Nea Kameni the measurements of gases (mainly CO₂) have been done instead manually with a consequent more limited in time data collection. Other atmospheric datasets comprehend the meteorological data, mainly pressure and temperature. Finally, we collected data on thermal anomalies and SO₂ columns from satellites at some selected volcanoes. Regarding solid Earth, the gas data will be compared with other datasets represented by the distribution of faults on Mt Etna and of fractures in the smaller Nea Kameni island, and with the datasets on the distribution of seismicity in the same time frame. The aforementioned datasets will serve the need of the following potential users and business cases (associate datasets and results with real world examples): Geohazard organizations and consultancies, civil protection, geologists, civil aviation agencies.

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 9 - Main active faults of Mt Etna and main historic seismic events.

Figure 10 - Simplified geological map of Mt Etna with main active faults and the sites of indoor radon measurements. The urbanized areas are shown in light gray. PFS, Pernicana fault system; RFS, Ragalna fault system; TFS, Timpe fault system; FF, Fiandaca fault; TF, Trecastagni fault; ATF, Aci Trezza fault.

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 11 - 2016-2018 Radon measurements recorded at Mt Etna in the Giarre municipality. Radon concentration are presented as daily (blue line), weekly (red), and long-term (green) averages. No data interruption occurred during the acquisition period.

2.2.3. Data and Products for Meteorological services

For developing and validating the Atmospheric Service (A1), we will employ the following datasets:

Table 6 - Dataset for Meteorological Services.

DATASETS – A1			
id	Name of Dataset	Type	Source
1	ATHENS THERMOPOLIS	Eddy covariance	ENTA
2	ATHENS THERMOPOLIS	AIRCRAFT- three level VARIANCES METHOD	ENTA
3	VOA-Gr STATION	Eddy covariance	ENTA and at www.unitus.it
4	VOA-Gr STATION	Gradient method at 4 heights	ENTA
5	ATHENS THERMOPOLIS	Gradient method at 5 different heights	ENTA
6	Copernicus DATABASE	various	ECMWF

The data obtained in the “Athens Thermopolis” and financed by the ESA, will be made available so that users can try our algorithms to obtain fluxes of GHGs, energy and momentum above a city. From our publications one can also obtain an algorithm that indicates anthropogenic fluxes of energy, in an urban environment. The use of tried algorithms for the calculation of GHGs, energy and momentum from aircraft flights will also be supported as a service to users. Eddy Covariance and gradient method from met

towers algorithms will also be provided. The Copernicus database, refers also to fluxes but data are sporadic and of unknown validity. Below are some filtered, processed and explained flux data from our Climate Watch Station VOAGr in northern Greece. This station is part of and provides data to the European Fluxes Database Cluster (<http://www.europe-fluxdata.eu/>) with data deposited at “database@unitus.it”.

2.2.3.1. Flux densities examples from VOAGr

Spectral flux density is the quantity that describes the rate at which energy is transferred by electromagnetic radiation through a (real or virtual) surface, per surface area and per wavelength. The Climate Watch Station VOAGr (installed in northern Greece) shown in the picture below provides flux densities data that will be used in NEANIAS, which need to be processed through calculation methods.

Figure 12 - VOAGr MET Tower.

Below one can find in graphical form flux densities from our VOAGr MET TOWER using different flux densities calculating methods. The most commonly used method is Eddy Covariance since it requires the vertical velocity datum covarying with the concentration of a scalar. Hence flux densities calculations are relatively straightforward. However, these parameters have to scan a number of frequencies, a fact that requires fast response sensors, not always available. The aerodynamic gradient method and its derivatives is based on the fact that scalars vary with height according to the prevailing atmospheric stability. Determination of horizontal wind velocities and “slow” determinations of scalars suffice to calculate fluxes, based for example on the "Monin-Obukhov" similarity theory.

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 13 - VOAGr MET TOWER graphical form flux densities using different flux densities calculating methods.

2.2.3.2. Open data sources

There are different services capable of providing useful information regarding meteorological information, with some of them providing publicly available open data, listed below.

2.2.3.2.1. OpenWeather

OpenWeather⁴ is an online service that provides historical, current and forecast data. Depending on the data/service that is intended to use, it can be free or paid. The complete list of the available parameters and units that the service provides can be found at <https://openweathermap.org/current>, with the following table giving a brief summary of the available data:

Table 7 - OpenWeather Dataset from its service.

Name	Available
Temperature (min/max)	Yes
Humidity	Yes
Pressure (sea / ground level)	Yes
Wind (speed / direction)	Yes
Clouds	Yes
Precipitation	Yes
Snow	Yes
Visibility	Yes
Sunrise / Sunset	Yes
UV Index	Yes

Regarding the API, the following table provides some insights about it:

Table 8 - OpenWeather API conditions.

Characteristic	Details
Calls per minute	60
Search by city Name/ID/Coordinates	Yes
Current weather	Yes
Forecast	5 Days, 3-hour intervals
Calls per day (historical)	5000 (paid)
Historical weather	1 month back (paid)

2.2.3.2.2. IPMA

IPMA⁵ is the Portuguese service holding the biggest national network of meteorological infra-structures that provides current weather and forecast data⁶. The last one can be aggregated by the day (until 3 days) or local (until 5 days). The following table gives a summary of the available data:

Table 9 - IPMA Dataset from its service.

Name	Available
Temperature (min/max)	Yes

⁴ <https://openweathermap.org/>

⁵ <http://www.ipma.pt/pt/index.html>

⁶ <https://api.ipma.pt/>

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Humidity	No
Pressure (sea / ground level)	No
Wind (speed / direction)	Yes (by classes)
Clouds	Yes * (inferred by weather classes)
Precipitation	Yes * (inferred by weather classes)
Snow	Yes * (inferred by weather classes)
Visibility	No
Sunrise / Sunset	No
UV Index	No

Regarding the API, the following table gives some insights about it:

Table 10 - IPMA API conditions.

Characteristic	Details
Calls per minute	Infinite
Search by city Name/ID/Coordinates	No/Yes/No
Current weather	Yes
Forecast	No (current weather is a forecast)
Calls per day (historical)	Yes, 5 days
Historical weather	No

2.2.3.2.3. **DarkSky**

DarkSky⁷ provides current and forecast (minutely, hourly and daily) weather and alerts. The complete list of the available parameters and units that the service provides can be found at <https://darksky.net/dev/docs>. The following table gives a summary of the available data:

Table 11 - DarkSky Dataset from its service.

Name	Available
Temperature (min/max)	Yes
Humidity	Yes
Pressure (sea / ground level)	Yes (only one, not distinguished)
Wind (speed / direction)	Yes
Clouds	Yes
Precipitation	Yes
Precipitation probability	Yes
Precipitation Intensity/accumulation	Yes
Snow	Yes
Visibility	Yes
Sunrise / Sunset	Yes
UV Index	Yes
Temperature High/Low times	Yes
Dew Point	Yes
Apparent Temperature	Yes

Regarding the API, the following table gives some insights about it:

⁷ <https://darksky.net/>

Table 12 - DarkSky API conditions.

Characteristic	Details
Calls per day	1000 (free)
Search by city Name/ID/Coordinates	Yes
Current weather	Yes
Forecast	Yes (next 48h)
Historical weather	Yes

At the time of writing this deliverable, the service has already been acquired by Apple⁸, which will certainly impose restrictions to the usage of the service, therefore the consortium will continuously monitor the service's conditions to assess its practicality for EOSC and NEANIAS.

2.2.3.2.4. Agromonitoring

Agromonitoring⁹ is part of the OpenWeather company but focuses on data suitable for agricultural applications, it provides current, forecast and historical weather base on satellite data for a specific area. The complete list of the available parameters and units that the service provides can be found at <https://agromonitoring.com/api>. It also provides NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index), EVI (Enhanced Vegetation Index) and accumulated temperature and precipitation, soil temperature and moisture. It has basically the same data and API limits as OpenWeather, it only adds the Satellite imagery for the agricultural applications. The historical data requires a paid subscription.

2.2.3.2.5. AQICN

AQICN¹⁰ provides a worldwide Air Quality Index for different locations and cities. This service only provides the index for the air quality (AQI) and not the pollutants considered for its calculation. Regarding the API, the following table gives some insights about it:

Table 13 - AQICN API conditions.

Characteristic	Details
Quota	1000 per second
Search by city Name/ID/Coordinates	Yes
Current AQI	Yes
Historical AQI	No

2.2.3.3. Research Projects

In the following section, research projects that are relevant for NEANIAS regarding the Atmospheric services are analysed.

⁸ <https://www.businessinsider.com/apple-buys-dark-sky-app-grow-services-iphone-2020-4?op=1>

⁹ <https://agromonitoring.com/>

¹⁰ <https://aqicn.org/>

2.2.3.3.1. Copernicus

European Union's Earth Observation Programme, Copernicus¹¹, offers information services based on satellite Earth observation and non-space data. It delivers near-real-time data that can be used globally and regionally, served by a set of satellites and in-situ systems such as ground stations. The services that transform the gathered satellite and in-situ data into valuable datasets that ensure the monitoring of changes, allow better forecasts. The main areas where Copernicus focuses are Marine, Climate change, Security, Emergency, Land and Atmosphere¹².

The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) provides continuous data and information on atmospheric composition. It provides daily information on the global atmospheric composition, reactive gases, ozone, and aerosols. It also provides near-real-time and forecast (4 days) of the European air quality¹³.

Figure 14 - Copernicus online catalogue of data.

For the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service, the data catalogue and daily analyses and forecasts can be found at <https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/data> (shown in the above image).

2.2.3.3.2. ACTRIS

ACTRIS¹⁴ (Aerosol, Clouds, and Trace Gases Research Infrastructure) is the European Research Infrastructure for the observation of Aerosol, Clouds and Traces Gases. Serves a vast community of users working on atmospheric research, climate and Earth system and air quality models, satellite retrievals, weather analysis, and forecast systems by offering high-quality data and research infrastructure services for atmospheric aerosols, clouds, and trace gases. This research infrastructure aims to contribute in resolving societal and environmental challenges, such as air quality, health, sustainability, and

¹¹ <https://www.copernicus.eu/en>

¹² <https://www.copernicus.eu/en/about-copernicus/copernicus-brief>

¹³ <https://www.copernicus.eu/en/services/atmosphere>

¹⁴ <https://www.actris.eu/default.aspx>

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

climate change, by providing a platform for researchers to combine their efforts and by providing open datasets of aerosols, clouds, and trace gases¹⁵.

Figure 15 - ACTRIS Data Centre (an online portal for data).

The ACTRIS data portal can be found at <https://actris.nilu.no/>. It provides not only a way to explore the available datasets, but also a tool to plot the values for analysis, as seen below.

¹⁵ <https://www.actris.eu/about/actris/whatisactris.aspx>

Figure 16 - ACTRIS processing data through its portal.

2.2.3.3.3. *symbIoTe*

The **symbIoTe** (symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments, <https://www.symbiote-h2020.eu/>) project provided an interoperable mediation framework to enable the discovery and sharing of connected devices across different IoT platforms for rapid development of cross-platform IoT applications.

Within sybIoTe, the **Smart Mobility and Ecological Routing use-case** addresses the problem of inefficient transportation and poor air quality that many European cities face nowadays. This use case offers the ecologically most preferable routes for motorists, bicyclists and pedestrians based on the available traffic and environmental data acquired through various platforms. This scenario is extremely relevant for people who travel within the major European cities, since a constant exposure to pollutants can cause severe health problems. It is also of the interest of the municipalities' governing bodies that, by helping their citizens to avoid these health problems, they can reduce health care costs. Additionally, the use-case provided a way for users to search for Points of Interests, filtered by certain factors such as air quality, noise pollution and parking availability. sybIoTe empowered this use-case by providing platform interoperability, allowing for developers to easily access and handle data from different platforms and domains in the same manner.

sybIoTe Core Services are responsible for storing IoT meta-information about the platforms, their resources and domain models they are using. It also provides search, security, administration and monitoring features. Another layer, sybIoTe Cloud Services, provide a virtualization support for integrating IoT platforms and allowing unified and secured remote access to the observation data, services and actuators. The provided service is on the TRL 8, proposed to be included in the EOSC Portal¹⁶.

¹⁶ <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/symbiote>

2.3. Atmospheric Sector: Current Software and Services

In this section, each Atmospheric service developed within the Neanias project is presented and described in detail, especially regarding the inputs necessary for individual users.

2.3.1. [A1] – Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring service

ATMO-FLUD is a service that can be used for calculating flux densities of momentum energy and scalars using two methods, Eddy Covariance and Gradient Method. There are various use cases such as monitoring greenhouse gas emissions, depositions, i.e., flux densities. These algorithms were chosen because they are the state-of-the-art in this domain.

Eddy Covariance:

In micrometeorology, the eddy covariance method is used to determine turbulent fluxes across a boundary layer interface, as for example, the land-atmosphere or the sea-atmosphere interface. The method is theoretically simple in concept, provided that fast response sensors (determining atmospheric parameters and scalars at high frequency) are available. It can directly determine flux densities of energy, momentum and gases or aerosol, in a semi-continuous manner. However, in dealing with a “complex system” such as the atmosphere, nothing is simple. A number of assumptions have to be taken into account and a number of pre calculation and post calculation data treatment procedures have to be carried out.

Firstly, as the name indicates, the method determines the co variation of turbulent vertical motion of air and the vertical turbulent motion of energy, or momentum, or mass. In describing turbulent motion, one has to deconvolute the mean value of the motion from the fluctuation of the mean motion as can be described by the “Reynold’s deconvolution principle”. The turbulent motion of air at any instant can be defined as the mean value of its velocity vector (the vertical velocity in our case) plus the value of its fluctuation from the mean. Of course, the choice of the ensemble of values to calculate this mean is described later (in most of our cases it is 20-30 minutes as determined by the calculated ogives, vide infra). Hence, for example, in eddy covariance the product of the two means of the vertical wind velocity in one hand (w) and the mean of a mass concentration of a scalar (s) can be mathematically depicted as $F = \overline{w \cdot s} + \overline{w' \cdot s'} = \overline{w} \cdot \overline{s}$

which means that the product of the two co-varying means is the mean of their products since the average of their variations are/or should always be zero (this is also a check for correctness of our calculations). Hence, the flux F of a scalar is defined as the mean of the product of the vertical wind velocity and the “value” of the scalar. The typical example here is:

Flux of CO₂ above a surface= mean of the vertical wind velocity in meters per second times the mean concentration of CO₂, in mg per cubic meter, resulting in a flux density of

$$\text{mg. m}^{-2}.\text{s}^{-1}$$

The convention here is that upward fluxes (from the interface) have a positive sign and downward fluxes (to the interface) have a negative sign. The flux density is conceptually the flow of mass from or to a unit area of the interface per unit time. In distinguishing the term “Flux density” from the term “Flux”, the latter is the flow of mass from a defined area for a specifically defined length of time, thus having units mass (flow) per area.

The assumptions for the above statistical calculations are numerous. The most important are discussed here. Flux calculations assume that the area under consideration has no horizontal gradient of the scalar, or otherwise, that there is a homogeneous horizontal concentration for the calculation of vertical flux. Secondly, that this assumption holds for the averaging period that we calculate flux density. Or again, otherwise, that there is no advection of scalar to this area. Thirdly, that the vertical wind velocity is determined at very high frequencies, together with scalar determination at the same high frequencies so that most of turbulent transport can be captured. This means expensive ultrasonic anemometer(s) and even more expensive dedicated sensors. Fourthly, that the sensors determine mass per unit volume or that corrections involving the “ideal gas equation” are made within the instrument or offline. Other data pretreatment and post calculations corrections are listed below:

- I. Because of electronic and natural noise (e.g. insects interfere with the anemometer signal), data have to be “despiked”. This means that a datum peak, greater than 3 times the standard deviation of the mean ensemble value is deleted and replaced by the mean of its previous and next values. This is the simplest case.
- II. Frequencies lower than the ones recorded and that appear in the time series, should be filtered out by a high pass filter. This means that only “high frequencies” of the co-spectra are considered because data of low frequency are due to large eddies and indicate advection. These large eddies should be filtered out. The high pass filter is initiated by the “block averaging” statistical treatment.
- III. Planar rotation is a correction that may be needed to correct the leveling of the sonic anemometer to avoid vertical wind data contamination by horizontal wind.
- IV. The cumulative sum of the co-varying frequencies indicates at what time this sum reaches a steady value, whereby this is considered as the optimum time for

ensemble averaging of the co-spectra. Such a process is called the “ogives representation”.

- V. The foot print of the area that is “sampled” by the instrumentation placed above the turbulent roughness layer, is calculated after the fetch (the length of the field away from the placed sensors) is calculated. Fetch and footprint are horizontal wind velocity and atmospheric stability depended.

DESCRIPTION OF DATA INPUT TO THE ALGORITHM OF EDDY COVARIANCE FLUX DENSITIES CALCULATIONS

1. When initiating a new execution of the algorithm, the user provides an input file and defines the following parameters:

a. Time period (default value in tenths of seconds: 18000 ==> Acceptable values: 3000 (5 minutes), 6000 (10 minutes), 9000 (15 minutes), 12000 (20 minutes), 15000 (25 minutes), 18000 (30 minutes). Time period depends on the values given by the ogive analysis.

b. Limit (default value): 3.5 times the standard deviation from the mean value of the ensemble. Ensemble is defined in point a. above.

c. Angle that the sonic faces the horizontal wind streamlines. For unidirectional ultrasonic anemometers this angle has to be user defined, with angle values up to 360 placed in both boxes. *CAUTION: ONLY for directional sonic anemometers an arc of 120 degrees should be considered. This means 60 degrees either side of the horizontal wind streamlines, whereby, the anemometer faces directly the streamlines. e.g. for wind coming from the north (0 degrees), arc should be from 300 degrees to 60 degrees. For wind coming from the south east (135 degrees), arc should be from 75 degrees to 195 degrees. This means that for the first example the value 300 should be placed in the first box and 60 in the second, etc. Values that are obtained beyond the 120 degrees horizontal wind streamlines arc, may give erroneous results.

d. For omnidirectional sonic anemometers values in both boxes should be the same and represent the horizontal wind direction streamlines.

2. NB: If we have a lot of empty values graphs 18 and 19 will not appear.

Gradient Method:

The atmosphere is in contact with both the surface of terrestrial ecosystems and the surface of the oceans. The laws of physics that govern the transport of pollutants at the interface and through it to the other medium (to or from the atmosphere, the land or the ocean) are similar but with several diversifications described below.

The horizontal wind speed at the surface of the earth is governed by its anomalies which slow it down. In neutral atmospheric conditions, where the vertical turbulence in the atmosphere is governed only from the horizontal flow of the wind, this horizontal speed of the wind increases with height (or fluctuates near the earth's surface) in a logarithmic way:

$$\bar{u} = u_*/K_* \times \ln\left(\frac{z-d}{z_0}\right)$$

where:

z_0 is an empirical parameter called “surface roughness length”

$K_* = 0.4$ is the Von Karman, constant

u_* = is the friction velocity as a measure of the wind speed deceleration due to the roughness of the surface

z = Height of wind speed measurement.

d = Height of surface obstruction (e.g. mean height of forest trees, mean height of corn field).

It is a usual practice in the above cases to find u_* and z_0 for the surface that is studied to measure the horizontal wind speed at four (4) or more height points. Also at these four points to measure the temperature and the concentration of water vapour or the concentration of gases of which we wanted to measure the fluxes from or to the surface. The flux of a gas from or to the surface is governed by the simple law of turbulent diffusion.

For the calculation of “a flux” F with the gradient method one utilizes the bulk Richardson number to establish the degree of turbulence of the “measurement field”:

$$R_i = \frac{g}{T} \frac{(\partial T / \partial z)}{(\partial u / \partial z)^2}$$

where:

g is the acceleration due to gravity,

T is the temperature in K at the mean determination height

the bracketed term in the nominator is the temperature gradient

and the squared bracketed term in the denominator is the wind speed gradient

Richardson Classification number Comment

For atmospheric conditions classified as **stable**, the R_i is > 0.25 there exists no vertical mixing, weak winds, strong inversion, dampened mechanical turbulence and a negligible spreading of a pollutant or scalar. Also for the **stable** classification where $0 < R_i < 0.25$, the mechanical turbulence is weakened by stable stratification. For the **neutral** classification where $R_i = 0$, there exists only mechanical turbulence. For the

unstable classification where $-0.03 < Ri < 0$ there exists only mechanical turbulence and convection. Also for the **unstable** conditions where $Ri < -0.04$ convection is predominant, winds are weak, vertical motion is strong, and a pollutant or scalar spreads rapidly vertically and horizontally. For simplification reasons, one can use the two cases below, where $Ri \geq 0$ and $Ri \leq 0$.

In further considering the gradient flux theory we explore the concept of the dimensionless physical parameters of heat and velocity deceleration which are defined as follows:

$$\Phi_M = \frac{K(z-d)}{u_*} \frac{du}{dz}$$

and

$$\Phi_H = \frac{K(z-d)u_*pC_p}{H} \times \frac{dT}{dz}$$

where:

p is the air density at constant pressure

C_p is the air thermal capacity at constant pressure

H is the vertical heat flux

However, the Φ_H and Φ_M values are determined empirically for $Ri \leq 0$ (unstable-turbulent conditions) and $Ri \geq 0$ (stable-laminar- stratified conditions) as follows:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Phi_M &= (1 - 16z/L)^{-1/4} \\ \Phi_H &= (1 - 16z/L)^{-1/2} \end{aligned} \right\} Ri \leq 0$$

$\kappa \alpha z/L \approx Ri$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \Phi_M &= \Phi_H = (1 + 5.2 \times z/L) \\ z/L &= Ri / (1 - 5.2 Ri) \end{aligned} \right\} Ri > 0$$

Hence having established Ri and calculated the appropriate Φ_H and Φ_M the flux density F , using the gradient method can be calculated from the following equation:

$$F = \frac{K^2 \frac{du}{d[\ln(z-d)]} \times \frac{dc}{d[\ln(z-d)]}}{\Phi_M \times \Phi_H}$$

where:

u is the wind speed and c is the concentration of the scalar
all other symbols have been defined previously

DESCRIPTION OF DATA INPUT TO THE ALGORITHM OF GRADIENT METHOD

When initiating a new execution of the algorithm, the user provides an input file and defines the following parameters:

1. Period: Time period for averaging depends on the value given by the user and not exceeding 30 minutes.
2. Limit: ‘Limit’ times the standard deviation from the mean value of the ensemble of the chosen period for averaging.
3. Heights: Heights of sensors. In the requested parameters of ATMO-FLUD web application Heights = [height1, height2, height3, height4].
4. Z: The height at which each of the four anemometers is installed.

As mentioned above in section 2.2.3.1 and in the section 3.1.1 below, all software for the flux density implementation was already available in the form of a Matlab executable with a number of subroutines for filtering data, calculating fluxes with a number of methods and inter-comparing these methods (see figure below). The format of data inputs to Matlab is ASCII. Furthermore, according to the EU Directives 2008/50/EU and 2015/1480/EU there should be a national reference point to validate these calculations. However, as it is common practice among atmospheric (and other) scientists “round-robin” exercises will reveal errors, accuracy, and repeatability of the results. Adjustments can be easily implemented, once the “basic structure” of the software is in place.

Figure 17 - Comparison of the determination Sensible Heat fluxes by Eddy Covariance and Variances methods.

2.3.2. [A2] – Monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions service

The A2 service, focused on monitoring atmospheric components in active tectonic and volcanic regions, has been implemented **in two separate services**.

After the initial co-design sessions between the providers and end-users belonging to the Atmospheric community and based on the D3.1 [1], two different services were required in order to satisfy the needs of the end-users. More specifically:

- ✓ the **first** one that has been implemented in the framework of NEANIAS is “**ATMO-STRESS**”, that produces maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data.
- ✓ the **second** one that has been implemented in the framework of NEANIAS is “**ATMO-SEISM**” service, that relates the seismicity of an active tectonic region and the variation of gas emission in the atmosphere.

2.3.2.1. A2.1-ATMO-STRESS

The ATMO-Stress service is designed to rebuild the stress field of a study area. More in detail, the service interpolates the stress trajectories for a specific stress component (σ_1 , σ_2 , σ_3 , σ_{HMAX} , σ_{HMIN}) expected of lying on the same horizontal plane. The main goal of the service is to understand the stress state of the Earth’s crust, which has a strong influence on the conditions that may allow the movement of fluids (including gases) across the crust, encouraging or inhibiting their ascent to the surface and their emission in the atmosphere.

The service is based on the already existing software “Lissage” by Lee and Angelier (1994) [4] and works with a broad range of input, like field geological data, earthquake focal mechanisms, in-situ geotechnical stress measurements.

It accepts .txt file and .xls files as input, reporting the geographic coordinates of the sites where data have been collected, the value of the direction of the chosen stress component to be interpolated, and the angular error (Theta). Once the input file has been uploaded in the service, it is possible to select the field to associate to each parameter, selecting the label of the desired column of the input file (Figure 18). Then, the imported values can be interpolated by the service with two different methods (“Polynomial” or “Distance Weight”), and with three orders of interpolation (“Global”, “Medium” or “Local”). The interpolation parameters can be estimated automatically by the service, using the automatic values given by Lee and Angelier (1994) [4], or they can be typed manually by the user.

Figure 18 - Screenshot of the Atmo-Stress service, showing the possibility of selecting data fields from the columns of the input file.

The outputs can be given as grid or trajectories maps; in both cases, the maps are visualized directly on the website (Figure 19), and then can be downloaded as a zip folder, where they are presented as .png, .tif, .shp (that can be open in GIS softwares), and .kml (that can be opened in Google Earth) files.

Figure 19 - Screenshot of the Atmo-Stress service, showing the trajectories map of σ_3 in a rift zone in Northern Iceland, obtained with the Polynomial interpolation, global order, and visualized on the website. The result can also be downloaded.

This service represents an improvement of an already existing software, overcoming some limitations of the older version: it works on modern PCs, it is user-friendly and, furthermore, it allows to export outputs which can be opened in GIS environment and Google Earth. These characteristics make it useful for the geological community, especially for structural geologists and volcanologists, but also for industrial stakeholders and national institutional level institutes such as Civil Protection agencies, which can use it to monitor the fluid movements in the crust and gas emission in the atmosphere.

2.3.2.2. A2.2-ATMO-SEISM

The main goal of the ATMO-SEISM service is to correlate gas emissions with earthquakes parameters and atmospheric conditions, to improve the comprehension of the interplay between tectonic activity, volcanism and gas release (e.g. radon, CO₂, SO₂ etc.) through faults, fractures or volcanic craters. Indeed, in active tectonic and volcanic regions, gas emissions depend on atmospheric conditions but also on the stress state acting in the crust, on faults and fractures. In particular, the monitoring of radon emission is crucial for Civil Protection, not only for its relation with seismic and volcanic hazard, but also for its dangerousness for human health; for this reason, the service is focused especially on radon, although it is possible to use it also with other gases, like CO₂ and SO₂.

ATMO-SEISM has been developed as a Jupyter Notebook service hosted in a dedicated JupyterHub deployment. The ATMO-SEISM service, with the use of a developed Python Package (pyradon), enables users to comparingly process and analyse gas releases and earthquake datasets and plot useful visualizations.

The input files accepted by the service are .csv and Excel files (both .xls and .xlsx). The input datasets which must be imported are two: the first including information about gas and atmospheric conditions with data and hour, geographic coordinates of latitude and longitude of the gas measurements, the value of gas emission, temperature and pressure; the second including information about earthquakes, with data and hour, geographic coordinates of latitude and longitude of the earthquake, depth of the hypocentre and magnitude of the event.

The service then relates all the inserted parameters, returning the following graphs as outputs: firstly, it returns the graph showing the relation between data/hour and atmospheric conditions (Figure 20.a). Then, thanks to the inserted values of temperature, pressure and gas emission, it calculates the correlation between them, obtaining the values of predicted gas emission, i.e. the gas emission due to atmospheric conditions variations, which should not be considered. Subtracting these predicted values from the measured values, the service finally obtains the filtered values, which can be correlated to tectonic activity (Figure 20.b). Moreover, the service shows a map of the location of hypocentres, and plots longitude vs depth of the hypocentre (Figure 20.c), latitude vs depth and magnitude vs depth. Considering the inserted magnitude of the earthquake, the service then calculates the released energy, and it finally relates it with the number of seismic events and with gas emission (Figure 20.d).

Figure 20 - Examples of outputs of Atmo-Seism, obtained from input datasets collected on Mt. Etna in 2016; (a) Data vs temperature and pressure; (b) Filtered radon values; (c) Longitude vs depth of the earthquake hypocentre; (d) Released energy and radon emission

In this case, the service is completely new, but it is inspired to the work presented by Neri et al. (2016); indeed, the service offers the possibility to automatically correlate gas emission, atmospheric conditions, and earthquake parameters, without the need of doing manually all the calculations and allowing to save time, especially for huge

amount of data. These characteristics make it useful for Civil Protection agencies, which can use it to monitor the gas emission in tectonic and volcanic active areas, especially radon, and for researchers and volcanologists, who can monitor the state of stress of an active volcano measuring gas emission in the atmosphere.

2.3.3. [A3] – Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service

Air quality (AQ) forecasting has gained recognition in the last decades in the research world, taking into account that it allows people to obtain future trends in a digital format. There are several platforms that are dedicated to provide air quality forecasts at a regional/global scale (e.g. Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) mentioned before; World Air Quality Forecast - <https://waqi.info/forecast/#/>; AirNow - <https://airnow.gov/>; NOAA's National Weather Service - <https://airquality.weather.gov/>). However, the number of studies that are dedicated to provide urban air quality forecast with a high spatial resolution are very few (London Air - <https://www.londonair.org.uk/LondonAir/nowcast.aspx>; AIRPARIF - <https://www.airparif.asso.fr/>; Urban Air@ - <https://www.numtech.fr/actualites.php?id=172>; Tchepel et al., 2020 [5]). Thus, the advance in simulation of urban air pollution must be rooted in methods that support forecasting.

At urban scale, the complex spatial and temporal variation of the pollutants' concentration in the atmosphere is a result of several factors such as meteorology, the effect of emission sources (local and background contributions) and urban morphology (i.e. presence of buildings and obstacles). Besides the difficulty to deliver urban air quality forecasts given the nature of variations of pollutants concentration in urban context, the NEANIAS project aims to provide a free service capable of executing air quality forecasts. Therefore, the AQ modelling system has to be based on models/products that are open-source.

To cope with these challenges, the NEANIAS project is working on providing a service, named ATMO-4CAST, that enables to map the pollutants concentration for a specific area with high spatial resolution. The service also provides weather forecasts, which enable the visualisation of different parameters such as temperature, precipitation, and others in a map.

2.3.3.1 Weather forecasting service

ATMO-4CAST provides the possibility to make weather predictions by means of the Advanced Research Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF-ARW) modelling system. The WRF-ARW is suitable for use in a broad range of applications from urban to regional scale studies. This model has two classes of simulations: ideal or real initialisation. Given the purpose of ATMO-4CAST, the service developed only simulates the last class. In a way of simplifying the compilation of data, the service developed requires only the WRF Preprocessing System (WPS) input data and the definition of both namelist inputs (configuration files). There are mainly two input methods available:

- GRIB1/GRIB2 formatted data along with configuration files;
- JSON formatted data and configurations (JSON structure detailed in the documentation).

To run the first stage of the WRF model (i.e. WPS) one needs meteorological data that may be provided by global weather models such as GFS (Global Forecasting Service)¹⁷. This data is provided in GRIB format, which will be internally processed by the service through the `ungrib` executable (generate intermediate format data) and then by the `metgrid` program (see Figure 21). Both programs are set in the `namelist.wps`.

Figure 21- ATMO-4CAST structure for GRIB method (input files in orange).

Also, a `Vtable` file is requested for the provided GRIB data. The `Vtables` are used by the `ungrib` program that reads GRIB files, “degrib” the data, and writes the data in a simple format called the intermediate format. The GRIB files contain time-varying meteorological fields and are typically from another regional or global model, such as NCEP’s NAM or GFS models. However, these files usually contain more fields than needed to initialise WRF. The `ungrib` uses these tables to define which fields to extract from the GRIB file and write to the intermediate format. `Vtables` may be also provided by GFS and other datasets (e.g. ECMWF, NCEP/NCAR Reanalysis archived at NCAR). Finally, the service requests the definition of the configuration files: (i) `namelist.wps`, (ii) `namelist.input`. While the `namelist.wps` enables to define each WPS program (`geogrid`, `ungrib` and `metgrid` programs), the `namelist.input` is used to run the `real.exe` and then the `wrf.exe` programs by using as input the data provided by the `metgrid` program.

For the JSON method, the service requires input data on meteorology and WRF configurations, both in JSON format. This method follows a similar logic to the input method previously mentioned. In fact, it is only a simplification/conversion of the same inputs into JSON format. To achieve this, the historical data required for the WPS stage is provided in a JSON file, and the configurations (both `namelist.wps` and `namelist.input`) are provided in a second JSON file. This separation allows easier manipulation and inspections of the configurations since the first file usually becomes very large in size. A detailed description on how these files should be constructed in

¹⁷ Global Forecasting Service (available <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/weather-climate-models/global-forecast>)

order to be successfully read by the service is provided in the documentation of the service¹⁸.

After the user compiles the required data, this may be directly uploaded in the service. Also, this data may be stored and managed using NEANIAS Data storage/sharing core service (Nextcloud). Moreover, the demo files provided may be used to test the service, before making weather predictions with their own datasets.

2.3.3.2 Air quality forecasting service

The ATMO-4CAST will also provide air quality estimations based on the Lagrangian model AUSTAL2000 (under development). This model was developed by the German Federal Environment Agency and enables to access locally the dispersion of pollutants in a flat or a complex terrain.

AUSTAL2000 has been applied in different European air quality studies and projects. Its popularity is due to the model's source code being free, the extensive guidance documents and also due to the program's ease of adjustment as language support and UTM coordinates (Janicke et al., 2007 [6]). The application of the AUSTAL2000 model will provide the urban air quality with a high resolution. However, to obtain the spatial distribution of pollutants for a specific area, the user needs to provide the service with information on:

- main parameters defined in the austal2000.txt file, such as information of coordinates and reference points of the study area, the output grid resolution and contains parameters that characterise the emission sources;
- spatial distribution of emission induced by local sources, especially road traffic for urban areas (series.dmna and austal2000.txt);
- terrain profiles (terrain.grid file);
- building information (location and height, building.dmna file).

The emissions induced by traffic sources may be obtained with the application of emission models. One of the categories of emission models is based on an average speed approach. Some examples of this category are COPERT and Qtraffic. COPERT (<http://copert.emisia.com/>) is a free software used to calculate regulated and unregulated traffic-related emissions for national emission inventories. QTraffic software has been developed by the University of Coimbra and applied for urban scale modelling (Dias et al., 2019 [7]). Both models are based on the European guidelines (EEA, 2019 [8]) for emission factors. However, while COPERT provides the estimation of emissions at an aggregate level, QTraffic was designed to provide emissions at a road segment level. This particularity of QTraffic facilitates the implementation of a more high-resolution approach for air quality modelling. Therefore, the ATMO-4CAST service is adopting this model in the beginning of the modelling chain. To use this feature the user will need to provide traffic information regarding: volume of traffic at a road level; traffic speed; statistical information regarding vehicle technology and fuel properties.

In calculating dispersion, AUSTAL2000 allows the calculation of terrain effects and evaluation of the downwash effects caused by buildings (Langner and Klemm, 2011

¹⁸ JSON Structure Details (available here: https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a3-service/en/latest/json_structure.html#json-matrices-file)

[9]). The downwash effect of buildings occurs when effluent is emitted near a building and is displaced downwards by the airflow along and around buildings (Canepa, 2004 [10]). AUSTAL2000 considers the effects of topography and the presence of buildings in the calculation of dispersion through the TALdia wind field diagnostic model. This model creates a library of wind fields in the first place without the effects of buildings. Only, in a second step, does it take it into account by creating wind fields that contour the buildings and terrain through iterative processes. Its use is activated by using the gh parameter, corresponding to the file containing the digital terrain elevation model with the terrain heights in the calculation area, or by defining the buildings in the austal2000.txt file. AUSTAL2000 supports two different formats in the characterisation of the digital terrain elevation model: ascii file obtained through GIS tools or DMNA file. Buildings can be defined through parameters that define the position, height, length, angle of rotation of buildings or through a raster file through the rb parameter to be introduced in the austal2000.txt file (Janicke, 2009 [11]).

Moreover, weather forecast is another important input information for air quality forecast. Therefore, the AUSTAL2000 model is linked with the weather forecast of the ATMO-4CAST service. The WRF-ARW model provides information on wind direction, wind speed and atmospheric stability, which is necessary to define the series.dmna file used in the AUSTAL2000 model.

The AUSTAL2000 model will provide the dispersion of pollutants emitted locally, however, the urban air quality is a result of local and background contributions. Therefore, the service aims to link the AUSTAL2000 simulations with the background concentrations that may be obtained from the COPERNICUS services (<https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu/>). Copernicus is a European database that freely collects information from a set of satellites and in-situ systems such as ground stations. One of the six services available in COPERNICUS is the Atmosphere Monitoring Service, named CAMS. This service provides continuous data and information on atmospheric composition and is used to assess and forecast the AQ at global/regional scale.

In synthesis, Figure 22 provides the air quality modelling system structure and the inputs required by users in yellow.

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 22 - ATMO-4CAST air quality modelling system structure (input files in yellow).

2.4. User Requirements for Atmospheric Services

Considering the feedback provided by the several user communities described before (urban air quality authorities, geologists, geohazards and civil protection stakeholders, meteorological services, industry and energy decision makers, ecologists, rural and urban planners, as well as insurance and health stakeholders), the following user requirements have been initially formed like ‘User Stories’. A User Story is an instrument used in Agile software development to capture a description of a software feature from an end-user perspective. The User Story describes the type of user, what they want and why.

Table 14 - User Requirements for Atmospheric Services.

Id	End-User	User-requirement	Reason
R0	All targeted	Common AAI	To allow end-users to come back to their experiments, with a single account, and provide the system with logging and auditing capabilities.
R1	All targeted	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various formats	To process end-user data with different services and be able to store them and make them available to other users
R2	All targeted	Use datasets provided by the services	To test a service and learn its functionalities
R3	All targeted	Visualize raw data as well as resulting products and reports	For a first glance, viewing the raw/vendor data (map or mosaic etc.); inspect and evaluate the results
R4	All targeted	To access data from suitable on-line repositories and data sources	To have access to essential data for performing the tasks of each service and compute the corresponding results

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

R5	All targeted	Document the workflow	For quality assurance, traceability, reproducibility and backlogging
R6	All targeted	Export the results in various file formats	Facilitate the exchange of datasets between users
R7	Geologist	Correlate gas emissions (e.g. Radon) with earthquake events and atmospheric conditions in active tectonic regions	To study the dependencies between the monitored quantities
R8	Geologist	Produce maps of the regional stress field of a study area which are compatible with GIS environments	To study the relation of the stress field with the gas emissions in the area
R9	Urban air quality authority / Public health authority	Aggregate, harmonise and store cross-domain data from multiple sources (satellite, geospatial, in-situ)	To monitor/forecast the air quality of a region of interest
R10	Meteorologist	Aggregate, harmonise and store GHG flux related data from multiple sources (satellite, geospatial, in-situ)	To improve flux estimation and compute reliable GHG emissions on a regional / national scale
R11	Industry / Energy and power decision maker / Ecologist	Calculate the flux densities of GHG emissions	To monitor the emissions in a region of interest and formulate suitable management policies
R12	Rural / urban planner	Filter the GHG emissions and energy fluxes per area or location	To monitor the emissions in a region of interest and formulate suitable management policies
R13	Researchers/ governmental organisation	To upload their own measurements for computing flux densities	Produce their own flux densities with NEANIAS software
R14	Researchers/ governmental organisation	To employ available atmospheric data from NEANIAS for flux densities benchmarks and learning purposes	Produce their own flux densities
R15	Researchers/ Industry	To compare their own software with the NEANIAS developed one for flux densities estimation	Benchmark their own flux densities solution
R16	All targeted	Improve portability and reproducibility	To make methods / results / findings accessible to the public / scientific community

Then, the aforementioned user stories/ requirements were linked with a level of priority and value based on end-user recommendations. Also, the manner to confirm their acceptance was also marked down.

Table 15 - Acceptance criteria for user requirements.

Id	Priority	Value	Acceptance
R0	High	High	User can only access the service after logging in with a NEANIAS account.
R1	High	High	User Interface (UI) provides functionalities for uploading / downloading data, relying on a Data Transfer Service
R2	Low	Medium	Services provide pre-loaded datasets for testing their functionalities
R3	Medium	High	UI provides functionalities to visualize the data and the results

D3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

R4	Medium	High	Services provide access to selected external datasets and repositories which provide essential data for their operation
R5	Medium	Medium	Provide proper support to the logging, backloging, auditing and accounting functionalities offered by the core services
R6	Low	Medium	Implement data serialization processes supporting several widely-used data formats.
R7	High	High	Be able to examine correlations between gas emissions and any earthquake related events/ time series
R8	High	High	Be able to produce maps of a regional stress field
R9	High	High	Be able to fuse data from multiple sources for air quality monitoring
R10	High	High	Be able to aggregate atmospheric and flux related data on a regional / national scale
R11	High	High	Provide the capability to calculate flux densities of GHG emissions
R12	Medium	High	Be able to ask for data for a certain area given a polygon of coordinates
R13	High	High	The service will provide the capability to upload external data for computing flux densities
R14	Medium	High	Be able to employ available from NEANIAS data for flux density estimation
R15	High	High	Be able to upload and process data and download the result.
R16	Medium	High	Provide related services and be able to store and publish the parametrization corresponding to specific workflows / data

3. Co-design and Service Specifications

This section reports on the state of the Atmospheric Services (in TRL7) that are developed under the NEANIAS project.

3.1. Atmospheric services

3.1.1. [A1] – Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring service

As described in Section 2.3.1, **ATMO-FLUD** service can be used for calculating flux densities of momentum energy and scalars using two methods, Eddy Covariance and Gradient Method. The minimum size of the input data volume required depends on the period of data, and varies from 67kb to 2880kb. There is no strict maximum size for the input data volume. However, as the required resources depend on the size of the input, there is a physical limit, based on the available resources of the target infrastructure. We further analyze these requirements in Appendix I.

The core component of the service has been ported from Matlab to Python, while the service is provided via a Python Flask application, that allows access using either a user interface or a REST API. Thus, users are able to provide their own datasets, execute the provided algorithms, and access the generated results, either in text or in visualized format. The service has already been onboarded to EOSC, and it is integrated with most of the available NEANIAS core services; AAI, Logging, Accounting, Data Sharing, SMS, Monitoring. Finally, we are currently working on the integration of ATMO-FLUD with Zenodo, to allow the user to upload the generated artifacts of the service's execution. We further refer the interested user to the specifications of ATMO-FLUD in Appendix I.

3.1.2. [A2] – Monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions service

As explained in chapter 2.3.2., the A2 service has been implemented in two separate instances/services: **ATMO-STRESS (A2-1)** and **ATMO-SEISM (A2-2)**.

ATMO-STRESS produces maps of tectonic stress trajectories based on a series of local stress data. The input data volume depends on the dimensions of the studied areas; some examples of the input datasets used for the validation, listed in paragraph 4.2.1. of the Deliverable D3.6, have dimensions between 6 and 185 KB.

The core functionalities of ATMO-STRESS were based on the LISSAGE software (Lee and Angelier, 1994 [4]). User authentication and authorization is handled by the NEANIAS AAI service (C2). Logging and Accounting are handled by the corresponding NEANIAS services (C2). The service is also integrated with the NEANIAS file service for handling user files and file sharing. For the next service release, the improvements suggested in the Deliverable D3.6 after the user validation will be implemented. Specifically, functionality, usability and visualization will be improved based on the feedback of the users, and also the implementation of pipelines

for continuous integration and deployment is planned. Data and results will be published to Zenodo.

ATMO-SEISM correlates gas emission values and atmospheric parameters with seismic activity. The input data volume depends on the dimensions of the studied area, and on the temporal interval chosen for the analysis. The input files required to run the service are two: the first regarding atmospheric parameters and gas emission values, and the second regarding earthquake parameters. The input datasets used for the validation have dimensions between 351 and 5326 KB for the first file, and between 1 and 97 KB for the second one.

ATMO-SEISM has been developed as a Jupyter Notebook service hosted in a dedicated JupyterHub deployment. The ATMO-SEISM service, with the use of a developed Python Package (pyradon), enables users to comparatively process and analyze gas releases and earthquake datasets and plot useful visualizations. For the next service release, functionality and usability will be improved based on the user feedback available in the Deliverable D3.6. Furthermore, the integration with NEANIAS Logging and Accounting services (C2) is planned. Data and results will be published to Zenodo.

3.1.3. [A3] – Air quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting service

The current service, named **ATMO-4CAST**, is based on the weather forecast service and the air quality forecast service (under development). The input data volume required depends on the domain to be studied, the time selected for forecasting and the spatial resolution selected for the output grids. Some examples of the input datasets are provided in the ATMO-4CAST service, which varies from 458 KB to 2,32 GB.

This service has been developed to run as an API implemented in Python and is available in the NEANIAS catalogue. The ATMO-4CAST has been updated with the latest UI libraries and following the users' recommendations obtained from the service validation from Deliverable 3.4. For the next service release, it will be also updated with the recommendations from Deliverable 3.6. ATMO-4CAST has been deployed on the GARR Cloud Platform and integrated with the NEANIAS AAI and Accounting and Logging Services to validate the access to private data and support the end-users. The NEANIAS SMS is used to request access to the service and authorization to the public/private data. Furthermore, the service is planned to be onboarded into EOSC, making it available for the atmospheric community when the modelling chain is complete.

3.2. NEANIAS Atmospheric Services Co-design Specifications Released

Based on the requirements relevant to the atmospheric services, as they have been expressed by the users in the previous section, this sub-section defines corresponding specifications for the software development cycle.

Firstly, the service requirements have been categorized according to their type. Five different types have been identified, namely, storage, computing, cloud, functional and quality requirements. The first two types regard the access and utilization of storage and computational resources available to the services. Cloud requirements depend on the

features of the cloud infrastructure which will host the services. Functional requirements request for certain features to be made available from the services. Finally, quality requirements are enforced to monitor and evaluate the quality of the results produced by the services.

Another important factor in the process of co-designing the specifications of the atmospheric services is the ranking of each specification, based on the feasibility and the effort required to satisfy a specific requirement in relation to its value, as expressed by the users (Table 15). According to this, each specification defined to address a specific user requirement has been characterized as mandatory, convenient or optional. Table 16, defined in D3.1 [1], presents the atmospheric service specifications that were defined to meet the requirements expressed by the users. In this deliverable, the table was updated with the results of the validations of each service (D3.4 and D3.6). Therefore, it is possible to understand which of the user's requirements and service specifications have already been addressed. The vast majority have already been completed, and the remainder will be addressed in the latest release of the services. Moreover, the specifications that are not aligned with the objectives of the current developed services were removed. For instance, the R04-S04 was removed, since this functional requirement has already been addressed by NEANIAS Share Service (Nextcloud).

Table 16 - Co-Design Specifications.

Requirement			Ranking	Specifications			Validated Status for WP3 Service			
Req#	Requirement	Type of Req. (Computing / Storage / Cloud / etc.)	Mandatory / Convenient / Optional /	Spec#	Description of the required functionalities, software specification	Addressed by	Atmo-FLUD (A1)	Atmo-STRESS (A2-1)	Atmo-SEISM (A2-2)	Atmo-4CAST (A3)
R00	Common AAI	Cloud	Mandatory	S00	Common SSO for all NEANIAS services	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R01	Upload, store and possibly publish datasets of various formats	Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for uploading / downloading data to medium / long storage locations through well-known protocols (FTP, WebDAV, etc.) and make data FAIR when applicable	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Service specific per user storage space	Y
R02	Use datasets provided by the services	Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for accessing data made available by the service provider for testing and learning the functionalities of the service	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R03	Visualize raw data, resulting products and reports	Functional	Mandatory	S02	Each Atmospheric service implements task-specific reporting mechanisms	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
		Functional	Convenient	S03	Interface with NEANIAS visualization services for visualizing raw data and results	A1, A2, A3	N/A	N	N	N/A
R04	To access data from suitable on-line repositories and data sources	Functional	Mandatory	S01	Interface with suitable Data Transfer NEANIAS/EOSC services for accessing data made available by external repositories when provided through standard data protocols	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R05	Document the workflow	Cloud	Mandatory	S05	Atmospheric services implement suitable logging mechanisms and store meta-data describing the service parametrization	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Partly	Y
		Cloud	Mandatory	S06	Interface with AAI, auditing and other relevant NEANIAS services for collecting user-related information	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Partly	Y
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS data transfer and other relevant services for storing and publishing logs and the workflow related meta-data	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Partly	Y
R06	Export the results in various file formats	Functional	Mandatory	S07	Each service offers option to serialize the produced data in widely used file formats	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interfaces with NEANIAS data transfer services for storing the output data on suitable storage locations	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R07	Correlate gas emissions (e.g. Radon) with earthquake events and atmospheric conditions in active tectonic regions	Computing	Mandatory	S08	Compute correlation and other statistical quantities of interest between a set of relevant variables defined by the user	A2	-	-	Y	-
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for accessing data through standard data transfer protocols	A2	-	-	Y	-
		Functional	Mandatory	S04	Interface with task-specific services for accessing data through custom APIs	A2	-	-	Y	-
R08	Produce maps of the regional stress field of a study area which are compatible with GIS environments	Computing	Mandatory	S09	Compute stress field maps based on well-known interpolation methods (e.g. inverse distance weighting or bivariate polynomial function)	A2	-	Y	-	-
		Functional	Mandatory	S07	Support export to data formats compatible with GIS environments (e.g. geoTIFF, KML, geoJSON, etc.)	A2	-	Y	-	-
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for storing data using standard data transfer protocols	A2	-	Y	-	-
R09	Aggregate, harmonise and store cross-domain data from multiple sources (satellite, geospatial, in-situ) for air quality monitoring	Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for accessing and storing data through standard data transfer protocols	A3	-	-	-	Y
		Functional	Mandatory	S04	Interface with task-specific services for accessing data through custom APIs	A3	-	-	-	Currently not applicable
R10	Aggregate, harmonise and store GHG flux related data on a regional / national scale	Computing	Mandatory	S11	Aggregate and harmonize cross-domain GHG flux data	A1, A3	Y	-	-	N
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for accessing and storing data through standard data transfer protocols	A1, A3	Y	-	-	N
		Functional	Mandatory	S04	Interface with task-specific services for accessing data through custom APIs	A1, A3	Y	-	-	Currently not applicable

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

R11	Calculate the flux densities of GHG emissions	Computing	Mandatory	S12	Compute flux densities of GHG emissions (dynamic gradient calculations, eddy covariance)	A1	Y	-	-	-
R12	Filter the GHG emissions and energy fluxes per area or location	Functional	Mandatory	S14	EOSC service is able to filter data with geographies as input parameters	A3	-	-	-	N
R13	To upload their own measurements for computing flux densities	Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for storing user-provided data using standard data transfer protocols	A1	Y	-	-	-
R14	To employ available atmospheric data from NEANIAS for flux densities benchmarks and learning purposes	Quality	Mandatory	S13	Define default parametrization and example scenarios for testing / learning each provided service	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
R15	To compare their own software with the NEANIAS developed one for flux densities estimation	Quality	Mandatory	S02	Each service reports suitable evaluation metrics which allow for comparison with other related methods / software	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Y	Y
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS/EOSC Data Transfer services for uploading user reference results for comparison	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Partly	Partly
R16	Improve portability and reproducibility	Cloud	Mandatory	S05	Atmospheric services implement suitable logging mechanisms and store meta-data describing the service parametrization	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Partly	Y
		Storage	Mandatory	S01	Interface with NEANIAS data transfer and other relevant services for storing and publishing logs and the workflow related meta-data	A1, A2, A3	Y	Y	Partly	Y

4. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the requirements of the NEANIAS WP3 “Atmospheric Research Services” including a detailed description of the user communities, datasets and products involved as well as the research gap of software tools regarding three thematic services: A1 - Greenhouse gases flux density monitoring, A2 – Monitoring atmospheric perturbations and components in active tectonic regions, and A3 – Air Quality estimation, monitoring and forecasting. Furthermore, user requirements for the atmospheric sector have been defined and the technological specifications of the released atmospheric services toward satisfying those requirements have been summarised.

Atmospheric services went through two rounds of user validation tests (see deliverable D3.4 and D3.6). In summary, the first round of validations was made by a total of 30 users, while the second by 106 users. Overall, from the second round the user’s reported less error rates compared to the first round and the feedback were in most of the cases positive, however, they have indicated some improvements. The received user’s feedbacks will be important to upgrade the services' user interfaces, documentation and to specify clearer test sets for the next period and final release. Moreover, for the final release, we expect all the services to reach TRL 8 and be onboarded to the EOSC ecosystem.

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3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

List of acronyms

Acronym	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
API	Application Programming Interface
AQI	Air Quality Index
ASCII	American Standard Code for Information Interchange
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
EVI	Enhanced Vegetation Index
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GIS	Geographic Information System
H2020	Horizon 2020
IoT	Internet of Things
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
PC	Personal Computer
REST	Representational State Transfer
SMS	Short Message Service
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Appendix I – ATMO-FLUD Specifications

In this section, we refer to the specifications of ATMO-FLUD service, and how it provides access to the existing scientific algorithms of Eddy Covariance and Gradient method. Moreover, we define the format of the required input data, and we provide an estimation of the resources required to execute a new study, which depend on the size of the input data.

The algorithms provided via ATMO-FLUD have been modified during the lifetime of NEANIAS to meet the users' requirements. Initially, the Matlab code has been ported to Python, to allow its execution on a broader range of machines. This is the main component of the provided service, to which we refer as the scientific component of ATMO-FLUD. It allows the execution of either Eddy Covariance, or Gradient Method algorithms, by reading an input file, whose format we define bellow, and the input parameters defined in Section 2.3.1. Finally, each algorithm produces a series of graphs, a text file with the results of the calculation, and a pdf report with all graphs and a scientific background preamble, that is ready for publication.

The second component of the service is a web application, which provides the UI to the user, and allows her to do the following tasks:

1. Authenticate herself via the NEANIAS Authentication and Authorization Core Service. Currently the service supports Microsoft and Google accounts.
2. Start a new “study” or view past “studies”
 - a. A “study” is the execution of one of the two supported algorithms for a supplied input file, with algorithm-specific parameters.
 - b. A study starts a new background job that is executed at the NEANIAS production Kubernetes cluster. In this way, the web application provides access to the scientific component of the service.
3. Upload input and download results. For this, the user may optionally use the NEANIAS-specific Data Sharing Service, which is based on Nextcloud, to both provide the input data and obtain the results.

Furthermore, the web application provides a REST API, that allows other services to invoke new studies, monitor them, and obtain the results. Thus, ATMO-FLUD can be used programmatically by other services to create computational pipelines. A service must be authorized to use the API, using the NEANIAS Authentication and Authorization Core Service. The authorized calling service is using the API on behalf of a user. With the API in place, ATMO-FLUD can be part of complex execution pipelines, according to different business use cases. For more details on the API call specifications, please refer to its documentation (<https://docs.neanias.eu/projects/a1-service/en/latest/api.html>).

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

In the rest of this section, we will describe the options the service provides to its users regarding its input and output. We describe these options by referencing the user interface, but they are also available via the REST API.

When accessing the home page of the application the user can find information of the service, regarding the theory of Eddy Covariance and Gradient Method. The access to both the execution of new studies, and the listing of old studies is allowed after successful login via the NEANIAS AAI service.

Figure 23 - ATMO-FLUD Home page.

After successful login to the application, and by clicking the “new study” button the user is able to select the target algorithm to run, as displayed in the following image.

Figure 24 - ATMO-FLUD Algorithm selection page.

The following steps of using the service aim to collect the input data and the parameters required to start an instance of the scientific calculation. Initially, the user selects an input file, containing data to be processed by the target algorithm. ATMO-FLUD provides four different ways of providing input data to the service:

1. Demo file: the web application provides demo files, that can be used to quickly access the service, and assess the whole execution process. These files are stored in the NEANIAS Data Sharing Service, under the account of ATMO-FLUD.
2. User file shared with the service: each user of NEANIAS, has access to the Data Sharing Service, which, as we mentioned above is based on Nextcloud. The user can login to the Data Sharing Service, via the NEANIAS AAI, upload her files, and share them with the account of ATMO-FLUD. Then ATMO-FLUD can access these files, and present them to the owner user, as available files for input.
3. Direct upload: the user can upload data files directly from her local machine to the service. In contrast to the previous option, these files are deleted from the service's storage, after the completion of the requested study.
4. File URL: the user can provide a publicly accessible URL of a data file. Upon execution of the scientific component this file will be fetched, temporarily on the target machine that executes the requested study.

Figure 25 - ATMO-FLUD Input type selection page.

Bellow, we refer to the format of the required input for each of the provided algorithms

1) Eddy Covariance

Each row of the input file for the Eddy Covariance algorithm should contain the following fields, separated by a comma:

- a) Date-Time in the form: (2014-07-15 00:00:00)
- b) U_x (m/s): Horizontal wind velocity on the x axis, for the streamlines arriving at the directional sonic anemometer
- c) U_y (m/s): Vertical to x axis horizontal wind velocity
- d) U_z (m/s): Vertical to the interface wind velocity
- e) Sonic temperature T_s ($^{\circ}\text{C}$): as measured by the sonic anemometer and calibrated, in situ, by a hot wire temperature sensor
- f) Wind Direction (deg): horizontal wind direction defined by the sonic anemometer
- g) Wind Speed (m/s): as determined by the sonic anemometer before deconvolution to U_x and U_y .
- h) Air Pressure (mbar): as measured by an in situ barometer.
- i) Scalar concentration in units of mass per unit volume e.g. $\text{mg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$: as measured by the fast scalar sensor, it being of the open path (CORRECTIONS NEEDED), or of the closed path design.

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

An example of the ASCII file for the input of the 10Hz data is shown below:

```
2014-07-15 00:00:00,2.708,1.843,-
0.093,25.33,253.4,4.551,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.1,2.634,1.726,-
0.149,25.35,253.4,4.36,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.2,2.715,1.777,-
0.198,25.36,253.4,4.492,1010,0.00177525696271233
2014-07-15 00:00:00.3,2.656,1.806,-
0.225,25.38,253.4,4.462,1010,0.00177525696271233
```

In the following table we provide an estimation of the minimum size of the input file, according to the period of the data, regarding continuous data with time step 0.1 sec.

Period (min)	Minimum number of lines	Approximate size (kB)
5	6000	480
10	12000	960
15	18000	1440
20	24000	1920
25	30000	2400
30	36000	2880

There is not maximum allowed value in the size of the input file. However, note that the required memory needed to process a file, depends on the size of the input file. As a result, the target node should have available resources. On our infrastructure we place a Kubernetes job for a scientific calculation in a machine (worker node of the Kubernetes cluster) with the requested available resources. If the required resources for a calculation exceed the maximum resources of a single node, then the job could not be scheduled for execution. An estimation of the required resources is presented in the next table.

Input file size	Memory resources (MB)	CPU resources
< 500 MB	$\text{file_size} * 15 + 500$	1
> 500 MB	$\text{file_size} * 14 + 500$	1

2) Gradient Method

Each row of the input file for the Gradient Method algorithm should contain the following fields, separated by a comma:

- a) Time (Date-Time Record)
- b) Wind speed at height 1 (m/s)
- c) Wind speed at height 2 (m/s)
- d) Wind speed at height 3 (m/s)
- e) Wind speed at height 4 (m/s)
- f) Air Temperature at height 1 (degrees C)
- g) Air Temperature at height 2 (degrees C)
- h) Air Temperature at height 3 (degrees C)
- i) Air Temperature at height 4 (degrees C)
- j) Relative humidity height 1 (in %)
- k) Relative humidity height 2 (in %)
- l) Relative humidity height 3 (in %)
- m) Relative humidity height 4 (in %)
- n) At the reference height, Barometer (mbar)
- o) at the reference height, Wind Direction (degrees)

An example of the input is shown below:

2014-07-15

08:30:04,2.931,3.008,2.984,2.96,24.130,24.08,23.9,23.72,65.570,65.82,65.56,65.30000000000001,1009,230.000

2014-07-15

08:30:05,2.624,3.111,2.692,2.273,24.130,24.09,23.87,23.650000000000002,65.530,65.78,65.57,65.35999999999999,1008,229.900

2014-07-15

08:30:06,2.582,2.882,2.889,2.8959999999999995,24.140,24.08,23.91,23.740000000000002,65.470,65.75,65.57,65.38999999999999,1008,224.500

2014-07-15

08:30:07,2.957,3.067,3.045,3.0229999999999997,24.330,24.12,23.9,23.679999999999996,65.440,65.69,65.5,65.31,1009,224.900

In the following table we provide an estimation of the minimum size of the input file, according to the period of the data, regarding continuous data with time step 1 sec.

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Period (min)	Minimum number of lines	Approximate size (kB)
5	600	67
10	1200	134
15	1800	201
20	2400	268
25	3000	335
30	3600	402

There is not maximum allowed value in the size of the input file. However, note that the required memory needed to process a file, depends on the size of the input file. As a result, the target node should have available resources. On our infrastructure we place a Kubernetes job for a scientific calculation in a machine (worker node of the Kubernetes cluster) with the requested available resources. If the required resources for a calculation exceed the maximum resources of a single node, then the job could not be scheduled for execution. An estimation of the required resources is presented in the next table.

Input file size	Memory resources (MB)	CPU
*	$\text{file_size} * 12 + 400$	1

As soon as the user has selected the input data file for the calculation, she has to select the values of the required input parameters. We refer to the required parameters for each algorithm in Section 2.3.1. Finally, ATMO-FLUD provides a verification step of the selected input data and input parameters, so that the user avoids the execution of misconfigured studies.

The execution time of a study depends on the size of the input data file, as well as the available resources of the infrastructure at a specific period of time. To let the user be aware of how the calculation is progressing, ATMO-FLUD provides a “workflow” page, where the user can monitor the status of any study, including the current status, error messages in case of a failed studies, the step of the process, and the time required to execute each step of the process.

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Step	Progress	Time
Initialize:	██████████	16.63 seconds
Filtering:	██████████	0.10 seconds
Despiking:	██████████	12.94 seconds
Rotation:	██████████	2.11 seconds
Creating Blocks:	██████████	0.51 seconds
Footprint:	██████████	0.15 seconds
Spectra:	██████████	0.09 seconds
Plots:	██████████	2 minutes and 13.47 seconds
Exporting:	██████████	0.46 seconds
Generate report:	██████████	12.17 seconds

Figure 26 - ATMO-FLUD Job status and progress.

When a requested study is completed successfully, the “show results” button of the workflow page becomes clickable and the user is able to access the execution results. ATMO-FLUD provides a set of graphs in the results’ page of the calculation along with a set of download options.

Bellow we provide an example of these output graphs for each algorithm, and we describe the available download options:

1. Eddy Covariance

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Figure 27- ATMO-FLUD sample output 1.

Figure 28 - ATMO-FLUD sample output 2.

2. Gradient Method

Figure 29 - ATMO-FLUD sample output 3.

Figure 30 - ATMO-FLUD sample output 4

The available download options are as follows:

1. Report document: the pdf report with all graphs and a scientific background preamble, that is ready for publication.
2. Results.txt: the text file containing the results of the calculation.

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

3. Data in tar.gz: All the generated graphs, the pdf report and the results.txt in a tar.gz file.
4. Data in zip: All the generated graphs, the pdf report and the results.txt in a zip file.
5. Share output folder: The results of each execution are stored in a single folder in the Data Sharing Service, under the ATMO-FLUD's account. This option allows the user to request access to this folder in the form of a shared folder, in the Nextcloud terminology.

Furthermore, in the results page the user is able to provide feedback of her experience with the service, and the provided results. The feedback form is stored under the ATMO-FLUD's account in the Data Sharing service and it is anonymous. Finally, we are currently developing the NEANIAS integration solution with Zenodo, for allowing a user to publish the results of each study, via the results' page of the service.

Figure 31 - ATMO-FLUD user options after job completion.

The last available option provided to the user is access to past studies. There the user can monitor all the requested studies, along with the related information per each, such as the status, the provided inputs and download options, and has the option to be redirected to the workflow and the results page of a selected study. Moreover, the user can list results of only one algorithm, or of specific status, e.g., only the completed studies.

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

- home
- new study
- past studies
- documentation
- my online storage
- sign out

NEANIAS Atmospheric Flux Densities

Past executions of service for
Results sorted in reverse chronological order

Created at	Algorithm	Output folder	Input file	Period	Limit	Angle from	Angle to	Duration	Status	Actions
2021-01-25 10:25:53	Eddy covariance	Runs/atmo-flud_7cfd499a-1d26-4751-b887-9421b5fb6bd9_341	Demo/_small.dat	30 minutes	3.50	180	300	0.27 seconds	Failed	
2021-01-25 10:11:42	Eddy covariance	Runs/atmo-flud_7cfd499a-1d26-4751-b887-9421b5fb6bd9_340	Demo/_small.dat	30 minutes	3.50	180	300	-	Active	
2021-01-25 10:03:24	Eddy covariance	Runs/atmo-flud_7cfd499a-1d26-4751-b887-9421b5fb6bd9_339	Demo/_small.dat	30 minutes	3.50	180	300	32.95 seconds	Completed	

Figure 32 - ATMO-FLUD past studies.

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

Appendix II

List of End-users outside NEANIAS Consortium that their feedback on the requirements of the considered Atmospheric Services contributed to this deliverable.

#	Associated Entities/ Networks/ Initiatives/ User Communities	Letter ¹⁹
A1	Marine Geosciences Group – Institut de Physique du Globe de Paris (IPGP) - CNRS - France	LoI
A2	Earthquake Planning & Protection Organization (EPPO) - Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport - Greece	LoI
A3	Geodynamic Institute (GI) of National Observatory of Athens (NOA) - National Tsunami Early Warning Center (NTEWC) - Greece	LoI
A4	Hellenic Plate Observing System (HELPOS) - NOA - Greece	LoI
A5	Square Kilometre Array (SKA) Organization - UK	LoS
A6	GEANT pan-European network (www.geant.org)	LoI
A7	Greek Research and Technology Network S.A. (GRNET S.A.) - Greece	LoI
A8	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)	LoIn
A9	DRASSM - Ministère de la Culture - France	LoIn
A10	Greek Copernicus Relay Network - Space Cluster (Si-Cluster) Corallia - Greece	LoI
A11	United Nations - Sustainable Development Solutions Network (UN-SDSN) - Greece	LoI
A12	EIT Climate-KIC Hub Greece	LoI
A13	LifeWatchGreece Research Infrastructure - Greece	LoI
A14	OpenAIRE https://www.openaire.eu/	LoC
A15	International Lithosphere Program (ILP) https://www.scl-ilp.org/	LoI
A16	Democritus Research Center (DRC) - Greek representing for ICOS RI (Integrated Carbon Observation System Research Infrastructure) & ACTRIS (Aerosol, Clouds and Trace Gases RI)	LoI
A17	National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics (OGS) - Italy	LoI
A18	EDF Énergies Nouvelles (EDF) - France https://www.edf-renouvelables.com/en/	LoI

	External Advisors (EA) / Members of Extended Strategic Steering Committee (ExSSC)	Letter
1	Dr Jorge Sanchez-Papaspiliou , Member of the si-Cluster Steering Board, Chief Strategy & Financial Officer, Corallia, the Innovation Unit of ATHENA	yes
2	Dr. Yan Grange , LOFAR Software Developer, member of Science Data Centre at ASTRON, the Netherlands Institute for Radio Astronomy	yes
3	Dr Javier Escartin , Head of the Marine Geosciences Group, Institute de Physique du Globe de Paris - CNRS -France	yes
4	Prof. Paul D. Williams , Professor of Atmospheric Science, University of Reading (UoR), UK	yes
5	Dr. Sofia Vallecorsa , Computer Engineer, CERN openlab	yes
6	Dr. Paolo DiViaco , Coordinator of the OGS DIAM-PROS unit, Vice-director of the RIMA (marine research and technologies) department of the OGS.	yes
7	Dr. Vicki Ferrini , Marine Geology & Geophysics - Columbia University - USA	yes

¹⁹ Letter of Intent (**LoIn**), Letter of Support (**LoS**), Letter of Interest (**LoI**), Letter of Commitment (**LoC**)
All letters can be found at the end of this Section

3.2 Atmospheric Research Services Report on Requirements and Specifications

8	Dr. Bianca Amaro. Coordinator of the Brazilian Open Science Program at the Brazilian Institute of Science and Technology Information (IBICT), President of the Federated Network of Institutional Repositories of Scientific Publications (<i>LA Referencia</i>)	<i>yes</i>
9	Judit Fazekas – Paragh , M.Sc. Head of Education and Research Support Department in University of Debrecen, University and National Library / NOAD of Hungary	<i>yes</i>